

Improved Reduced-Order Model for PLL Instability Investigations

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ABSTRACT There is a rapid increase in the installed capacity of offshore wind power plants (WPPs) worldwide, and the trend will continue in the context of the recent EU energy crisis and the Ukraine war. As the share of the capacity of wind power plants increases in power systems, it is essential that WPPs can stay connected with the grid during different operational events and provide ancillary services. Recent research has identified the Phase Locked Loop (PLL) converter control as a contributing factor to instabilities driven by large-signal disturbances (i.e. severe grid faults). This type of instability is referred to as grid-synchronisation stability (GSS). In light of this, grid codes are being revised to secure the connection of WPPs and specify the services that need to be provided. To study GSS, it is essential to model the wind turbine (WT) system and grid conditions accurately. However, the actual WT models are often unavailable, black-boxed, or computationally too heavy to model in detail. Thus, simplified reduced-order models resembling the actual system behaviour are the need of the hour. This paper presents an improved reduced-order model that considers a systematic approach to modelling the misalignment of the PLL angle in the converter states. Moreover, it considers the time-varying parameters and the step changes of initial conditions after fault triggering, which otherwise are neglected in the present literature. Based on transient stability studies, the improved reduced-order model correctly tracks the grid-angle post grid disturbances, and its trajectory is a good match compared to a detailed simulation mode in time domain.

INDEX TERMS Grid-synchronisation stability; Large-signal disturbance; PLL; Power converter; Reduced-order models.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN 2020, the worldwide offshore wind generation growth amounted to 25 TWh, with capacity additions of 6 GW, which are 29% and 12% more than 2019 respectively. To attain the 8000 TWh required in 2030 under the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario, it would be necessary to increase the annual offshore wind capacity growth to 80 GW [1]. With such rapid deployment of wind energy, the offshore wind power plants (WPPs) are also expected to play an essential role in the stability control of future power grids.

Traditionally, for transient/large-signal stability studies, the power system dynamics have been analysed using RMS simulations based on the assumption that stability is primarily influenced by the conventional power plant's electromechanical states [2]. However, under high renewable penetration conditions, the grid-tied power-electronic renewable generation exhibit very high control dynamics during

system transients such as fault ride-through (FRT) and fast-acting control actions. The time constants of such controls are smaller than those of a typical electromechanical phenomena, resulting in possible interactions with the electrical states of the system [3]. Therefore, current industry practices have evolved to use EMT simulations to investigate the transient stability of the grid-tied renewable generation.

Recent research from EMT studies has revealed that under weak grid conditions, grid-tied renewable generation with grid-following controls are prone to be small-signal unstable due to the interactions between the grid and its controls, in which the phase-locked-loop (PLL) plays a crucial role. Aside from this, another unstable phenomenon related to the PLL is emerging driven by large-signal disturbances (i.e. grid faults). This type of instability is referred to as grid-synchronisation stability (GSS) [4] [5].

In a wind turbine, PLL provides the instantaneous grid

voltage, phase angle and frequency. Despite the wide variety of PLL algorithms, the most widely used PLL is based on the synchronous reference frame (SRF) approach. In fact, some recent proposals entirely rely on the SRF-PLL dynamics, which are enhanced with a prefilter such as doubly decoupled SRF PLL, moving average SRF PLL, prefilter moving average SRF PLL [6]. In the absence of the modified PLL structure and considering only the basic version of SRF-PLL structure provides a less complex analysis.

In order to investigate GSS, it is essential to accurately model the WT converter system and the grid conditions. However, the actual EMT models are often unavailable, black-boxed, or computationally too heavy to model in detail. Simulating a manufacturer-provided EMT model for an entire wind farm can take long time, and stability can only be observed for the predefined events simulated. This could result in missing out on critically stable events. Hence, simplified reduced-order models resembling the original system behaviour have gained prominence in stability studies.

In [7], a methodology for a reduced-order model (ROM) based on power loss conservation in a solar farm is presented. A similar concept was extended to wind farms in [8]. Our present work only focuses on ROMs for wind turbines. Owing to several advantages, type-4 WT with back-to-back converters have gained prominence for offshore wind applications. In several works, including [9] [10], a type-4 WT is modelled just as a grid-side converter (GSC), where the turbine generator and the rotor-side converter (RSC) are not considered; instead, to observe their effects, the active power is simulated through a controlled current source. This significantly reduces the complexity of the WT model.

For a GSC, in [11]- [14], the fast system dynamics are neglected when analysing the slow PLL dynamics. As a result, the inner current loop is approximated as a unity gain. Consequently, the type-4 WT is simply modelled as a controlled current source with its phase angle regulated by an SRF-PLL. Furthermore, in [13], the SRF-PLL is decomposed into two feedback loops - "grid synchronisation loop" and "self-synchronisation loop", and the authors show how the low-frequency PLL dynamics are affected when the impedances of grid changes. In [14], the SRF-PLL is approximated as a synchronous machine, where the active current reference is constrained based on the system's stable equilibrium points.

In general, the WT ROMs in [11]- [14] address some non-linear characteristics, such as low-frequency PLL dynamics, interactions between the PLL and the system, and the impact of weak grids on the transient system behaviour. However, there is further scope for improvement. The existing ROMs lack a systematic approach to modelling the misalignment of the PLL angle. They also lack considering the time-varying parameters and neglect the jumps in initial conditions at the instant of the fault triggering. The ROMs must behave similar to a detailed EMT model; otherwise, the application of such ROMs will be limited to certain cases.

This paper aims to improve the WT ROMs to investigate grid-synchronisation stability. Time-domain studies are also

presented to support the improved performance. The main contribution in this paper includes,

- 1) A systematic approach is proposed to model the misalignment of the PLL frame and the system reference frame. It is known that the PLL misalignment causes a wrong measurement of the real-world signals, which can cause instability in the controls. This work will present a clear modelling approach, including the system and control reference frames voltages and currents of the converter.
- 2) An improved filter bus voltage equation, which results in a time-varying WT ROM. The time-varying parameters, such as a change in grid frequency, change in fault current injections, and change in grid voltage, have been considered in the proposed ROM, which otherwise have been neglected in the existing literature.
- 3) An analytical equation to calculate the jump in initial conditions post grid disturbances. It is known that different initial conditions will lead to a different trajectory that may later converge/diverge from the equilibrium point. A slightly different initial condition may result in an unstable system which may originally be stable. It will be shown that the proposed set of equations to calculate phase/frequency jumps matches the trajectories of a detailed EMT WT model.

The proposed WT ROM is computationally faster than detailed EMT models owing to its reduced-order nature. Since assumptions are considerably reduced, the proposed ROM is highly accurate over a wide range of frequencies. The proposed ROM also has a higher degree of application since the time-varying terms are considered. Several grid disturbances are discussed and simulated in the paper. Section II presents the methodology for the improved reduced-order model of the WT converter system and the grid. Section III presents the reduced-order model's performance and is compared against a detailed WT simulation model in PSCAD. Finally, Section IV presents the conclusion.

II. ANALYSIS OF GRID-SYNCHRONISATION STABILITY

Fig. 1 is presented in order to better explain the grid-synchronisation instability event physically. During severe grid faults, the fault point voltage drops down close to zero. According to requirements in some grid codes, the wind turbines need to inject controlled active and reactive currents to an inductive impedance load, with a very low voltage at the terminal. For weak systems, the amount of active and reactive current injections during a fault is important for stability and if the fault is not cleared in time, the converter may lose synchronism. It must be noted that synchronisation instability concerns also other grid disturbances such as grid voltage phase jumps, large frequency change, and disconnection of transmission lines in the external grids, among others.

A. REDUCED ORDER MODEL OF WIND TURBINE

In this work, a type-4 WT with only the GSC is considered. Under grid faults, once the dc chopper is activated, the dc

FIGURE 1. Synchronisation instability of Wind turbines during large signal disturbance (i.e. severe grid faults).

voltage is assumed to be steady during the faults. Further, the inner current controller is considered fast enough to regulate the DQ-domain currents. Consequently, the dynamics of the inner current loop are avoided. This assumption is valid since fast system dynamics can be neglected when analysing the slow PLL dynamics.

Furthermore, the shunt capacitor of the filter is also not considered, where in the later section it will be shown that the capacitor impact on GSS is negligible when the current is controlled on the grid-side inductor of the LCL filter in the detailed WT model. Subsequently, the reduced-order representation of the WT and grid in the DQ domain is illustrated in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. System representation of ROM in the DQ domain.

A PLL with SRF approach is used since such a structure provides a less complex yet highly intuitive analysis. It is well known that the PLL misalignment causes a wrong measurement of the real-world signals, which can cause instability in the controls. Fig. 3a illustrates the control structure of an SRF PLL, while Fig. 3b presents the vector diagram describing the misalignment of the PLL angle in the converter states.

From Fig. 3b, the misalignment in converter currents and voltages can be written as (1) and (2).

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_d^c \\ v_q^c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{df}) & \sin(\theta_{df}) \\ -\sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_d^s \\ v_q^s \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 3. (a) SRF PLL control structure, (b) Frame misalignment between the system reference frame (dq^s) and converter reference frame (dq^c).

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_d^s \\ i_q^s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{df}) & -\sin(\theta_{df}) \\ \sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^c \\ i_q^c \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where, $\theta_{df} = (\theta_{PLL}^c - \theta_{PCC}^s)$; v_d^c , v_q^c , i_d^c and i_q^c are the converter voltage and currents in the converter reference frame. While v_d^s , v_q^s , i_d^s and i_q^s are the converter voltage and currents in the system reference frame. Equations (1) and (2) introduces nonlinearities in the control system.

It must be noted that the WT system is modelled in a DQ frame, rotating at a fixed frequency ω_0 . The grid frequency could be different, but that is addressed by assuming that the grid voltage in DQ is rotating with $(\omega_g - \omega_0)$. The parameters of the system are considered to be time-varying. This is used later in this paper to model different grid disturbances and fault current injection.

As per Fig. 2, based on superposition principle, (3) represents the DQ voltages at PCC in the system reference frame. It must be noted that in (3), \dot{L}_g represents the change in grid inductance during a grid disturbance. In steady state operation $\dot{L}_g = 0$. A systematic approach to modelling the misalignment of the PLL angle is presented in (3), (4) and (6), where all the converter states (voltage and currents) are transformed to the control reference frame.

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{pcc_d}^s \\ v_{pcc_q}^s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{gd} \\ v_{gq} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_g s + r_{Lg} + \dot{L}_g & -\omega_0 L_g \\ \omega_0 L_g & L_g s + r_{Lg} + \dot{L}_g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^s \\ i_q^s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_g \cos(\theta_g) \\ V_g \sin(\theta_g) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_g s + r_{Lg} + \dot{L}_g & -\omega_0 L_g \\ \omega_0 L_g & L_g s + r_{Lg} + \dot{L}_g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{df}) & -\sin(\theta_{df}) \\ \sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^c \\ i_q^c \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The RHS of (3) can be simplified as (4) by simply solving the derivatives in the equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{bmatrix} vpcc_d^s \\ vpcc_q^s \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} V_g \cos(\theta_g) \\ V_g \sin(\theta_g) \end{bmatrix} \\
&+ \begin{bmatrix} r_{Lg} + L_g & -\omega_0 L_g \\ \omega_0 L_g & r_{Lg} + L_g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{df}) & -\sin(\theta_{df}) \\ \sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^c \\ i_q^c \end{bmatrix} \\
&+ \frac{d(\theta_{df})}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} L_g & 0 \\ 0 & L_g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\sin(\theta_{df}) & -\cos(\theta_{df}) \\ \cos(\theta_{df}) & -\sin(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^c \\ i_q^c \end{bmatrix} \\
&+ \begin{bmatrix} L_g & 0 \\ 0 & L_g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{df}) & -\sin(\theta_{df}) \\ \sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_d^c \\ i_q^c \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In order to track θ_{df} , a standard SRF-PLL tries to keep $vpcc_q^c$ to zero, and also $\dot{\theta}_g = \omega_g - \omega_0$. The control equations of an SRF PLL are given by (5).

$$\theta_{df} = \int \left(k_p vpcc_q^c + k_i \int vpcc_q^c dt \right) dt \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{d^2(\theta_{df})}{dt^2} = k_p \frac{d}{dt} vpcc_q^c + k_i vpcc_q^c \quad (5b)$$

where, k_p and k_i are the PLL controller gains, while from (4),

$$\begin{aligned}
vpcc_q^c &= \begin{bmatrix} -\sin(\theta_{df}) & \cos(\theta_{df}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} vpcc_d^s \\ vpcc_q^s \end{bmatrix} \\
&= r_{Lg} i_q^c - V_g \sin(\theta_{df} - \theta_g) + \overline{(L_g i_q^c)} \\
&\quad + L_g i_d^c (\overline{(\theta_{df} - \theta_g)}) + L_g i_d^c \dot{\omega}_g
\end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is an improved PCC bus equation, where the third term ($\overline{(L_g i_q^c)}$) is a novelty of this paper. It should be noted that i_d^c , i_q^c , V_g , and ω_g are not necessarily time-invariant during the PLL synchronisation analysis, i.e. the grid frequency or a post fault active current recovery might change as a ramp function.

By considering a variable change $\delta = (\theta_{df} - \theta_g)$; (5) and (6) can be rewritten as (7).

$$\begin{aligned}
\ddot{\theta}_{df} &= k_p (\overline{r_{Lg} i_q^c} - \dot{V}_g \sin \delta - V_g \cos \delta \dot{\delta} + \overline{\overline{L_g i_q^c}} \\
&\quad + L_g i_d^c \ddot{\delta} + \overline{\overline{L_g i_d^c}} \dot{\delta} + L_g i_d^c \dot{\omega}_g + \overline{\overline{L_g i_d^c}} \omega_g) \\
&\quad + k_i (r_{Lg} i_q^c - V_g \sin \delta + \overline{\overline{L_g i_q^c}} + L_g i_d^c \dot{\delta} + L_g i_d^c \omega_g)
\end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, subtracting $\ddot{\theta}_g = \dot{\omega}_g$ from both sides of (7), and solving for $\ddot{\delta}$ results in a swing equation look alike,

$$M \ddot{\delta} = T_m - T_e - D \dot{\delta} \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= 1 - k_p L_g i_d^c \\
T_m &= k_p (\overline{r_{Lg} i_q^c} + \overline{\overline{L_g i_q^c}} + \overline{\overline{L_g i_d^c}} \omega_g) + k_i (r_{Lg} i_q^c \\
&\quad + \overline{\overline{L_g i_q^c}} + L_g i_d^c \omega_g) \\
T_e &= (k_i V_g \sin \delta + k_p \dot{V}_g \sin \delta) + M \dot{\omega}_g \\
D &= k_p (V_g \cos \delta - \overline{\overline{L_g i_d^c}}) - k_i L_g i_d^c
\end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

If a time-invariant model is considered, i.e. by removing the derivatives in (9), we obtain the same model discussed in [15]. The ROM can then be rewritten in ODE form as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ \frac{1}{M} (T'_m - T'_e - D' x_2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where, $x_1 = \delta$ and $x_2 = \dot{\delta}$, and

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= 1 - k_p L_g i_d^c \\
T'_m &= k_i (r_{Lg} i_q^c + L_g i_d^c \omega_g) \\
T'_e &= k_i V_g \sin \delta \\
D' &= k_p V_g \cos \delta - k_i L_g i_d^c
\end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, if a system parameter varies over time, such as post-fault active current ramp injection from the converter, the ROM can then be rewritten in ODE form as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ \frac{1}{M} (T''_m - T''_e - D'' x_2) \\ i_d^{c,ramp} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where, $x_1 = \delta$, $x_2 = \dot{\delta}$ and $x_3 = i_d^c$, and

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= 1 - k_p L_g x_3 \\
T''_m &= k_p (L_g i_d^{c,ramp} \omega_g) + k_i (r_{Lg} i_q^c + L_g x_3 \omega_g) \\
T''_e &= k_i V_g \sin \delta \\
D'' &= k_p (V_g \cos \delta - L_g i_d^{c,ramp}) - k_i L_g x_3
\end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, for system parameter variation such as ramp in the grid frequency, the ROM can be formulated by considering the grid-frequency derivatives defined in (9).

B. INITIAL VALUE AFTER A DISTURBANCE

When the system parameters change continuously, the state variables also continuously change. However, if there is a step-change in the system, e.g. due to a fault, there will be an impulse in the state equations, as (9) contains derivatives of parameters. The easiest way to deal with this discontinuity is to solve the ODEs piece-wise. The ODE can be solved numerically in periods where there is no step-change in the parameters, and it is enough to update the initial values at the beginning of each period to address the step changes.

1) Jump in initial conditions for δ

Jumps in θ_{df} are dependent on the derivatives in (5a), where the integral of the second term is zero for a very short time around the event time, since $\dot{\delta}$ is bounded. Hence, the change in θ_{df} can be represented as,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta[\theta_{df}] &= \int k_p \left(\frac{d}{dt} (L_g i_q^c) + L_g i_d^c \frac{d}{dt} \delta \right) dt \\
&= \int k_p d(L_g i_q^c) = \Delta[k_p L_g i_q^c]
\end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where, $\Delta[X] = X_{post-event} - X_{pre-event}$. Further, subtracting $\Delta[\theta_g]$ from both sides of (14) results in (15) that describes the jump in initial conditions for δ post disturbance,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta[\delta] &= \Delta[k_p L_g i_q^c] - \Delta[\theta_g] \\
&= \Delta[k_p L_g i_q^c - \theta_g]
\end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

2) Jump in initial conditions for δ

The method described in section II-B1, can be similarly applied to obtain the analytical equation for the change in the PLL frequency. For frequency we have,

$$\dot{\theta}_{df} = k_p v p c c_q^c + k_i \int v p c c_q^c dt \quad (16)$$

The second term in the right-hand side of (16) can be treated similar to (14).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta[\dot{\theta}_{df}] &= \Delta[k_p v p c c_q^c] + \Delta[k_i L_g i_q^c] \\ &= \Delta[k_p r L_g i_q^c] - \Delta[k_p V_g \sin \delta] + \Delta[k_p (\overline{L_g i_q^c})] \\ &\quad + \Delta[k_p L_g i_d^c \dot{\delta}] + \Delta[k_p L_g i_d^c \omega_g] + \Delta[k_i L_g i_q^c] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

By replacing,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta[k_p L_g i_d^c \dot{\delta}] &= k_p L_{g_{po}} i_{d_{po}}^c \dot{\delta}_{po} - k_p L_{g_{pr}} i_{d_{pr}}^c \dot{\delta}_{pr} \\ &= k_p L_{g_{po}} i_{d_{po}}^c (\Delta[\dot{\delta}] + \dot{\delta}_{pr}) - k_p L_{g_{pr}} i_{d_{pr}}^c \dot{\delta}_{pr} \\ &= \Delta[k_p L_g i_d^c] \dot{\delta}_{pr} + k_p L_{g_{po}} i_{d_{po}}^c \Delta[\dot{\delta}] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

and subtracting $\Delta[\dot{\theta}_g]$ from both sides of (18) results in,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta[\dot{\delta}] &= \frac{1}{1 - k_p L_{g_{po}} i_{d_{po}}^c} \Delta[k_p r L_g i_q^c - k_p V_g \sin \delta + k_p (\overline{L_g i_q^c})] \\ &\quad + k_p L_g i_d^c \omega_g + k_i L_g i_q^c - \dot{\theta}_g + \Delta[k_p L_g i_d^c] \dot{\delta}_{pr} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where, subscript *pr* and *po* is the pre-event and post-event units, respectively. To better understand (15) and (19), it is advised to go to sections III-A.

III. CASE STUDIES

In this section, the performance of the proposed ROM is analysed and is compared against an EMT switching simulation model of a WT in PSCAD (CIGRE benchmark model, C4.49) [13]. Table 1 presents the parameters describing the WT system considered in this study. The proposed ROM is tested against grid disturbances such as grid phase jumps, frequency change, grid voltage sags, fault ride-through and grid impedance change.

TABLE 1. SYSTEM AND CONTROL PARAMETERS [13]

Symbol	Description	Value
S_b	Rated power	12 MVA
V_g	Nominal grid voltage (L-N, pk)	$690 \sqrt{2/3}$ V
V_{dc}	DC-link voltage	1.38 kV
f_0	Rated frequency	50 Hz
r_c, L_c	Converter-side inductor (pu)	0.005, 0.1
r_f, C_f	Filter capacitor (pu)	0.0757, 0.3
r_{Lg}, L_g	Grid-side inductor (pu)	0.0063, 0.06
i_d^c, i_q^c	Pre-disturbance active and reactive currents (pu)	1.0, -0.1
K_{cc}	Current controller design: $k_p k_i$	0.05, 0.3
K_{pll}	SRF PLL design: $k_p k_i$	0.025, 1.5

The PLL gains are chosen to obtain an oscillatory PLL behavior. The current is controlled on the grid-side inductor of the LCL filter in the detailed EMT WT model.

A. GRID VOLTAGE PHASE ANGLE JUMP

As discussed in section II-B, a step-change in the system parameters can cause a discontinuity in the solution of (8). To better present this, a simulation is performed where the grid phase angle is stepped up from 0° to 20° at $t=0.1$ sec. Consequently, two time periods are defined, one before the step and one after. The analysis of the first period (before the step) can be neglected as it is assumed that the step is applied when the system is at the equilibrium point, as shown in (20).

$$\delta_{pr} = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{r L_g i_q^c + L_g \omega_g i_d^c}{V_g} \right) \text{ and } \dot{\delta}_{pr} = 0 \quad (20)$$

As per (15), a 20° phase jump in θ_g causes a negative 20° jump in δ . The PLL angle is constant during the step because there is no other parameter change, and the PLL needs time to synchronise to the new angle. However, according to (19), this angle shift causes a step-change in the PLL frequency:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\delta}_{po} &= \frac{k_p}{1 - k_p L_{g_{po}} i_{d_{po}}^c} (V_g \sin \delta_{pr} - V_g \sin \delta_{po}) \\ &= 4.9312 \text{ rad/s} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

FIGURE 4. System response after 20° phase jump in grid voltage, (a) zoomed-in view at the instant of disturbance, (b) response until steady state.

It can be seen from Fig. 4a that the jump in δ and $\dot{\delta}$ is identical to the one calculated in (18) and (19). It is seen

that the PSCAD $\hat{\delta}$ has a slight overshoot and delay, this can be accounted for by the finite current controller bandwidth in PSCAD simulations, and the infinite current controller bandwidth considered in the ROM. However, the trajectories until the steady state are similar to the one obtained from PSCAD simulations, as shown in Fig. 4b.

B. GRID FREQUENCY VARIATION

The grid frequency is changed by a 10Hz/s ramp from 50Hz to 52Hz. Since no step-change occurs, the continuity in the trajectories is preserved before, during and after the ramp (see Fig. 5). A very low amplitude oscillation is observed in the PSCAD $\hat{\delta}$ trajectory, this is due to the PWM switching within the GSC. A good match in δ and $\hat{\delta}$ trajectory is observed between the PSCAD simulations and proposed ROM.

FIGURE 5. System response when grid frequency is changed by a 10Hz/s ramp from 50Hz to 52Hz.

C. GRID VOLTAGE SAG

The grid voltage magnitude is stepped down to 0.9 pu at $t=0.1$ sec. Similar to section III-A, the jumps in δ and $\hat{\delta}$ can be computed for a grid voltage sag. As per Fig. 6, a good match in δ and $\hat{\delta}$ trajectory is observed between the PSCAD simulations and proposed ROM.

D. FAULT RIDE THROUGH

In this case study, a complete Fault ride through is simulated. When a symmetrical fault occurs (the grid voltage is stepped down to 5%), the active current is stepped down to 0.1 pu, and the reactive current is stepped up to -1 pu. When the fault is cleared after 100 ms (the voltage is stepped up back to 1pu), the reactive current is set to pre-fault value; however, the active current is ramped up (eg. $2.84e4$ A/s), not to stress the mechanical structure. The sequence of events can be observed in Fig. 7 (sub-figure three). Based on the step changes, the entire simulation can be split into three periods, whose initial conditions can be computed from (15) and (19). As seen in Fig. 7, there is a good match between the proposed

FIGURE 6. System response after a grid voltage sag - 0.9 pu.

ROM and the detailed PSCAD model. The high dynamics in the PSCAD $\hat{\delta}$ can be neglected for the comparison in results.

FIGURE 7. System response during a FRT scenario, where the fault results in a severe voltage drop (0.05 pu).

E. GRID IMPEDANCE VARIATION

The last test case is a step-change in the grid impedance. This case can be compared to opening a line in the transmission system. The system, in this case (see Fig. 8), is stable when the grid inductance is changed from $3.78e-02$ mH to $7.57e-02$ mH. A good match in the trajectories is observed between the PSCAD simulations and proposed ROM.

In general, the performance of the proposed reduced order model is good compared to the PSCAD model (ignoring the dynamics of PWM and very slight delays introduced due to current control, in the PSCAD model). Through the time-domain simulations it was shown that the assumptions, such as neglecting the current controller due to slow PLL bandwidth, and ignoring the shunt capacitor filter considering the current is controlled at the grid side inductor of the

FIGURE 8. System response after sudden change in the grid impedance - $3.78\text{e-}02$ mH to $7.57\text{e-}02$ mH, emulating a line opening scenario.

LCL filter, are valid when analysing the large-signal/ grid-synchronisation stability of the type-4 WT. In the detailed PSCAD WT model, the dc bus voltage was considered constant during faults (considering the action of dc chopper), similar assumption was considered in ROM to reduce the model complexity, however, this may not always be true. In the light of this, it could be fruitful to modify the filter bus voltage (6) to take into account system dynamics/damping applicable due to dc bus voltage variation.

IV. CONCLUSION

An improved reduced-order model of a type-4 wind turbine to investigate large signal/ grid-synchronisation stability was developed. The methodology presents a systematic way to model the misalignment of the PLL angle in the converter states. A novel filter bus voltage equation is derived which results in a time-varying WT ROM. Further, the reduced-order model considers the jump in initial conditions post-disturbance, which otherwise has been neglected in the existing literature.

Based on the modelling and studies carried out in this paper, it is observed that post grid disturbances the proposed reduced-order WT model correctly tracks the angle and frequency, and its trajectory is a good match when compared to a detailed simulation model in PSCAD. Through the time-domain simulations it was shown that the assumptions such as neglecting the current controller due to slow PLL bandwidth, and ignoring the shunt capacitor filter, are valid considerations when analysing the large-signal/ grid-synchronisation stability of a type-4 WT.

The proposed WT ROM is computationally faster than detailed EMT models owing to its reduced-order nature. Since assumptions are considerably reduced in the modeling, the proposed ROM is highly accurate over a wider range of frequencies. The proposed ROM also has a higher degree of application since the time-varying terms are considered.

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